

Assessment of Hypocalcemia in Post Thyroidectomy Patients with Benign Thyroid Lesions: A Single Center Analysis from Tertiary Level Hospital in South India

Fathima Shehza¹, Syed Mohammed Afsal², Manju P.A.³, Raajalekshmi Ajit Kumar⁴

¹Junior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

²Associate Professor (CAP), Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

³Associate Professor (CAP), Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

⁴Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College, Ernakulam, Kerala, India.

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 25-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Raajalekshmi Ajit Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Thyroidectomy is a commonly conducted surgical procedure on a global scale. Hypocalcemia, resulting from either transitory or permanent hypoparathyroidism, is one of the most prevailing complications after thyroid surgery. The present study was done with the primary objective to know the prevalence of hypocalcemia through serum calcium levels in post-thyroidectomy patients.

Methods: The cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 patients admitted for thyroidectomy from August 2022 to August 2023 in the General Surgery Department of Government Medical College, Ernakulam. Demographics and clinical data were taken. A data capture sheet designed using Excel, was used to obtain and record data only relevant to this study was used. Statistical analysis was performed with statistical software SPSS version 25.0.

Results: The mean age of patients was 47.7±7.8 years. The percentage of male patients was 8% and female patients were 92%. Maximum patients were diagnosed with MNG (84%). The mean serum calcium levels at the pre-operative period were 9.08±2.1 and it was subsequently compared with day 1 (8.4±0.81), day 3 (8.5±0.63), day 5 (8.6±0.69), week 2 (8.9±0.81) and at 6 months (9.2±0.78) and the results were statistically significant (p<0.05).

Conclusion: Thyroidectomy is a surgical procedure that is generally safe and has minimal problems when conducted by a proficient surgeon. Hypocalcemia has emerged as a prevailing consequence following thyroidectomy. These issues lead to extended hospitalizations and increased expenses and burden on medical resources. Moreover, individuals who underwent total thyroidectomy exhibited the highest susceptibility to the development of post-thyroidectomy hypocalcemia.

Keywords: Benign, Hypocalcemia, Malignant, Outcome, Post-Operative, Thyroidectomy, Thyroid Lesion.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Thyroid disorder is one of the prevalent categories of endocrine gland diseases worldwide. They can be managed with either medical or surgical interventions. Thyroidectomy, whether sub-total or total, is a commonly conducted surgical procedure on a global scale [1,2]. Thyroidectomy is indicated in cases of ²compression symptoms, suspected or known malignancy, the existence of a solitary colloid nodule in patients under the age of 20, cosmetic grounds, thyroid dysfunction (especially hyperthyroidism) not amenable to medical management, and the development of a

complicated cyst or a cyst larger than 4cm in diameter [3].

Thyroid surgery is today regarded as a safe treatment because of advancements in anesthetic and operative procedures, antisepsis, surgical instruments, and better knowledge and understanding of thyroid anatomy and physiology [4,5]. Nevertheless, complications can arise after thyroid surgery. The consequences associated with this procedure encompass ²recurrent laryngeal nerve injury, hypocalcaemia, hematoma, seroma, stridor, loss of high-pitched voice, thoracic duct injury, wound infection, and tracheal injury [6].

The incidence of such complications is reduced when the surgical procedure is conducted by surgeons with extensive expertise, as indicated by the annual surgical volume of procedures performed [7]. An important disadvantage of total thyroidectomy is the high incidence of hypocalcemia due to parathyroid gland devascularization [8].

Inadequate production of PTH leads to hypocalcemia. According to reports, the incidence of transient hypocalcemia ranges from 2% to 53%. The etiology of transitory hypocalcemia following surgery remains unclear. The observed phenomenon could potentially be ascribed to transient hypoparathyroidism resulting from reversible ischemia or hypothermia of the parathyroid glands, or the release of endothelin-1. The acute phase reactant known as endothelin-1 has been observed to inhibit the production of parathyroid hormone (PTH). In individuals with transitory hypoparathyroidism, there has been an elevation in levels of endothelin-1 [9].

Additional explanations have been proposed to explain temporary low calcium levels that are not caused by hypoparathyroidism. Two conditions that can be observed are ¹Calcitonin release and hungry-bone syndrome. The thyroid gland synthesizes Calcitonin and hinders the process of bone resorption while promoting the elimination of calcium through the kidneys. The effects of this substance on calcium metabolism are contrary to those of PTH [9].

The majority of the patients who exhibit hypocalcemia following thyroidectomy initially do not display any symptoms. Several symptoms and signs, such as circumoral paraesthesia, alterations in mental status, tetany, carpopedal spasm, laryngospasm, seizures, QT prolongations on electrocardiogram (ECG), and even cardiac arrest can occur [10] due to hypocalcemia.

The appearance of the Chvostek sign or the Trousseau sign may also serve as an indicator of Hypocalcemia. The Chvostek sign is induced by applying pressure to the preauricular portion of the facial nerve, leading to the contraction of the muscles innervated by facial nerve. Trousseau sign refers to the occurrence of carpal spasm, which can be triggered by inflating the blood pressure cuff on the upper arm to a pressure exceeding 180mmHg [11].

If patients develop hypocalcemia post-operatively, they will require long-term follow-up and management on an in-patient or out-patient basis with oral or parenteral supplementation of calcium. Hypocalcemia symptoms affect the quality of life of patients. Also, in a developing country like India, it becomes a burden on medical resources. Hence the present study was done with a primary

objective to know the prevalence of hypocalcemia through serum calcium levels (which is a cost-effective and easily available biochemical test) in post-thyroidectomy patients. The secondary objective was to determine the correlation between pre-operative and post-operative calcium levels. This was done to review the calcium levels of these patients until six months after thyroidectomy and understand if pre-operative serum calcium assessment alone can be used to determine long term post-thyroidectomy calcium status i.e. can pre-operative serum calcium serve as predictor of whether patient will be normocalcemic or hypocalcemic.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted among patients admitted and undergoing thyroidectomy at the General Surgery Department of Government Medical College, Ernakulam from August 2022 to August 2023. The Ethical clearance was taken from the institutional ethical committee before the commencement of the study. The patients were asked to sign an informed consent form after explaining to them the complete procedure and inclusion of their demographic data in the study.

Based on the results of the previous literature publication [12] Hypocalcemia incidence is 18%, 95% confidence interval, and statistical power of 80%, the sample size for the cross-sectional study was calculated using $n = Z^2pq / d^2$ formula, and the calculated sample size was 114. Out of all the cases, 14 cases were lost to follow-up and hence only 100 cases data were examined. The study was conducted on all patients who underwent Total thyroidectomies of benign thyroid diseases at the department. Patients were selected on the basis of following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Both males and females
- Age: 20-75 years
- Underwent total thyroidectomy
- Proven Benign Thyroid disease/goiter
- Patients with pre-operatively documented serum calcium levels

Exclusion Criteria

- Known case of Hypocalcemia (pre-operatively)
- History of any previous thyroid surgeries
- Patients who had any history of parathyroid disorders/tumors and/or parathyroidectomy
- Recurrent laryngeal nerve injury
- Parathyroid gland in final histopathology report

The clinical data was collected retrospectively for all patients who underwent total thyroidectomy in the Department of General Surgery at Government Medical College, Ernakulam from August 2022 – August 2023.

The list of patients was obtained from OT records. The data was collected by retrieving case sheets of patients from the medical records department and their follow-up out-patient book. Serum calcium levels were recorded both before and after the operation. Serial monitoring of serum calcium levels was done at periodic intervals till the 6th month (details obtained from OP book). Patients were categorized into normo-calcaemic and hypocalcemia and those with Hypocalcemia were further classified into temporary or permanent hypocalcemia.

A data capture sheet designed using Excel was used to obtain and record only relevant data to this study was used. Statistical analysis was performed with statistical software SPSS version 25.0. In statistical analysis, continuous variables were presented as mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum

values. Categorical variables were expressed as frequency and percentages. To find the association between categorical variables Pearson chi-square test was used and to find association between quantitative variables correlate software was used.

Results

The mean age of patients was 47.7 ± 7.8 years, the percentage of male patients was 8% and female patients were 92%. Maximum patients were diagnosed to have Multinodular goiter (MNG) without retrosternal extension/atypia (84%) followed by colloid goiter (6%), MNG with retrosternal extension (3%), MNG with atypia (2%), Solitary Nodule Thyroid (SNT) (2%), MNG suspicious of follicular carcinoma (1%) (post HpR-benign) and lymphocytic thyroiditis (1%) as shown in table 1.

Table 1 Demographic and clinical profile of patients

Variable		Percentage / Mean
Mean Age (years)		47.07±7.8
Gender	Male	8%
	Female	92%
Diagnosis	MNG	84%
	MNG with retrosternal extension	3%
	MNG atypia	2%
	SNT	2%
	Nodular colloid	6%
	MNG TRIADS IV	1%
	Lymphocytic Thyroiditis	1%

The mean serum calcium levels during the pre-operative period were 9.08 ± 2.1 and it was compared with day 1 (8.4 ± 0.81), day 3 (8.5 ± 0.63), day 5 (8.6 ± 0.69), week 2 (8.9 ± 0.81) and at 6 months (9.2 ± 0.78) and the results were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2 Preoperative and postoperative serum calcium levels (immediate to subsequent follow-ups)

Mean serum calcium	Day 1 (post-operative)	Day 3 (post-operative)	Day 5 (post-operative)	Week 2 (post-operative)	6 Month (post-operative)
9.08±0.68	8.4±0.81	8.5±0.63	8.6±0.69	8.9±0.81	9.2±0.78
P value	0.005	0.012	0.001	0.002	0.001

Discussion

One common consequence linked to post-operative hypoparathyroidism is longer hospital stays and higher expenditures [5]. Research has demonstrated a correlation between a surgeon's experience and favorable clinical and financial results [7]. Post-operative Hypocalcemia may result from temporary or chronic hypoparathyroidism. According to a different study, there is a 63% chance of having Hypocalcemia [8]. The incidence of both temporary and persistent hypoparathyroidism ranges from 0.3% to 49% and 0% to 13% respectively, according to the literature [13]. Following a thyroidectomy, hypocalcemia is linked to the devascularization or loss of parathyroid gland tissues [3]. The parathyroid gland's venous

or arterial blood supply – or both – is compromised in definitive hypocalcemia. Tetany may develop within 12 hours following surgery. According to some authors, maintaining appropriate parathyroid activity requires only one active gland. However, according to other researchers, the restoration of normal function necessitates the presence of at least three parathyroid glands [8]. The intraoperative management of a de-vascularized parathyroid gland should involve reinserting the broken fragments into the sternocleidomastoid muscle [8].

A 6- to 12-month decline in serum calcium levels after thyroidectomy is known as temporary hypocalcemia. On the other hand, a reduction in calcium levels following a total thyroidectomy that lasts for more than a year is known as permanent

Hypocalcemia [14]. Our study involved a 6-month follow-up period. During the first 2-weeks of the follow-up, the serum calcium level was lower than it was before the surgery. However, after six months, the serum calcium level increased to reach the normal range, indicating a higher incidence of transient Hypocalcemia in most patients. Studies have reported incidences of 43% and 63% for transient Hypocalcemia [15,8]. According to another study, the incidence varied from 50% to 68%, especially following total thyroidectomy [14].

According to Trottier et al [16], a significant proportion of hypocalcemia rates have been documented in individuals who underwent complete thyroidectomies. According to Mehanna et al [17], the incidence of Hypocalcemia following total thyroidectomy ranged from 0.33 to 65%. Asari et al [18], documented a prevalence ranging from 1.6% to 50%. Kerimoglu et al [19], found that literature has consistently reported a high occurrence of hypocalcemia, ranging from 0.1% to 32%, after total thyroidectomy.

In a retrospective analysis undertaken by Karamanakis et al [5], a total of 2043 instances of thyroidectomy surgeries were examined at a university hospital in Greece. The findings of their investigation closely aligned with the results obtained in our own study. He reported a greater prevalence of hypocalcemia in patients who underwent total thyroidectomy, with a rate of 40.4%, compared to 24.7% in patients who underwent near-total thyroidectomy and 9.05% in patients who underwent partial thyroidectomy.

The study conducted by Fahmy et al [20] revealed that the prevalence of transient hypocalcemia varies between 5.4% and 26%, and permanent Hypocalcemia spans from 0.5% to 24%. According to Karamanakis et al [5], the prevalence of transient hypocalcemia has been seen to range from 6.9% to 46% in multiple investigations, whereas permanent hypocalcemia has been reported to occur at rates ranging from 0.4 to 33%.

According to the findings of Wiseman et al [21], the occurrence of transitory hypocalcemia following total thyroidectomy ranged from 17% to 26%. According to WU J et al [22], the third National audit conducted by the British Association of Endocrine and Thyroid Surgeons (BAETS) revealed that 30% of patients who underwent total thyroidectomy experienced transitory hypocalcemia, while approximately 7% developed permanent hypocalcemia that necessitated long-term care. In their study, Asari et al [18], documented a prevalence of 24.1% for temporary Hypocalcemia and 1.2% for persistent hypocalcemia subsequent to total thyroidectomy. Hypocalcemia typically manifests during a timeframe of 14 to 72 hours following surgery [16].

There has been a recent surge in interest regarding the identification of peri-operative variables that can serve as predictors for the occurrence of hypocalcemia following thyroidectomy [23]. The most pertinent measures and the optimal timing in predicting the post-operative transitory or permanent hypoparathyroidism are subjects of controversy [24]. Patients who can be classified as having a low risk of developing post-operative hypocalcemia may potentially receive treatment as outpatients for a short duration, leading to significant cost savings in healthcare [23].

The diligent observation of serum calcium levels has been consistently regarded as a customary practice in order to detect hypocalcemia following thyroidectomy caused by parathyroid insufficiency [23]. Nevertheless, the assessment of overall serum calcium levels is subject to inaccuracies, partially due to the dilution of haemoglobin after surgery [24]. Furthermore, the occurrence of calcium depletion during a 24-hour period is not a reaction that is exclusive to thyroid surgery. The post-operative changes in calcium and other electrolytes following surgeries of equivalent size and duration conducted outside the cervical region closely resemble those observed in patients who have undergone thyroidectomy. Conversely, the PTH level remained unchanged following these unrelated procedures [24].

Asari et al [18], determined that relying just on total serum calcium levels, evaluated within the initial 2 days after surgery, is not an accurate predictor of transitory hypoparathyroidism. Our study has revealed that relying solely on serial serum calcium monitoring can become a dependable indicator of post-thyroidectomy hypocalcemia. According to the findings of Kwon et al [25], the sensitivity of post-operative serum PTH in predicting post thyroidectomy hypocalcemia ranged from 64% to 100%, while specificity ranged from 72% to 100%. But serum PTH assessment is not widely available and is also a costlier test. Blood draw has to be timed for the accurate prediction of post-operative hypocalcemia.

Nevertheless, there is a lack of agreement regarding the specific threshold for parathyroid hormone (PTH) and the most suitable timing for its monitoring following a thyroidectomy. According to Tolone et al [24], the measurement of parathyroid hormone (PTH) on the initial day after total thyroidectomy has demonstrated its utility as a predictive method for post-thyroidectomy Hypocalcemia. The study suggests that assessing PTH concentration within 1-6 hours after thyroidectomy yields a higher level of accuracy in predicting Hypocalcemia. Terris et al [26], limited the scope and reported that a measurement conducted in the recovery room 1-2 hours after the surgery has been supported by multiple

independent studies as informative. Prior to the study, Asari et al^[18], provided commentary on the practice of monitoring parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels during surgery. They suggested that PTH levels that were below the normal range at the end of or immediately after the operation were strongly associated with postoperative hypoparathyroidism. This correlation appeared to enable early prediction, with a sensitivity and specificity ranging from 71% to 100%.

In a study conducted by Lombardi et al [27], it was shown that 15 out of 16 patients who experienced hypocalcemia after thyroidectomy exhibited post-operative parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels below 10pg/mL at both the 4- and 6-hour mark. The study demonstrated a specificity of 100%, a sensitivity of 94%, and an overall accuracy of 98%. In prospective research conducted by Lam et al [28], it was shown that of the 40 patients who experienced post-operative Hypocalcemia, all 12 patients exhibited post-operative parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels of 8pg/mL or lower within one hour after the surgery. In their study, Pattou et al [29] found that a post-operative parathyroid hormone (PTH) level of 12pg/mL or below was highly indicative of Hypocalcemia. However, the researchers did not specify the timeframe in which the PTH values were measured following the surgical procedure.

Terris et al [26] continue to suggest that regular calcium monitoring can be beneficial in the context of outpatient monitoring of thyroidectomy patients. This is possible even if post-operative PTH levels are determined, as a precautionary measure in case the PTH level is unexpectedly normal. Several prominent global health organizations, including The American Thyroid Association and The Australian Endocrine Surgeons Society, have implemented an outpatient thyroidectomy strategy. According to a Canadian study on outpatient thyroid surgery, it was found that a brief period of observation lasting 4-10 hours is deemed safe. Furthermore, the study indicated that thyroid surgery can be conducted as an outpatient procedure with a satisfactory rate of complications, as long as meticulous patient selection and pre-operative assessment are prioritized [30].

There are various limitations inherent in our investigation. Initially, the study was conducted at a single center and had a limited sample size. Furthermore, the study is retrospective. Insufficient evidence is available on the execution of a central neck dissection and the occurrence of subsequent surgeries. Serum PTH level comparison was not done. We require a larger sample size to determine pre-operative serum calcium alone can determine the incidence of post-operative Hypocalcemia. In order to address these constraints, our plan is to

carry out a prospective multicentre investigation in the near future.

Conclusion

In our study, most of the patients were found to have multinodular goiter. The study revealed that individuals who had a total thyroidectomy were at a higher risk of developing post-thyroidectomy hypocalcemia, mainly transient variant. The serum calcium levels of the patients in our study dropped immediately after the surgery but recovered within 6 months. Monitoring the calcium levels over time is a dependable and cost-effective method for identifying patients who are more likely to experience early post-operative hypocalcemia and for detecting long-term hypocalcemia after thyroid surgery. Additionally, the incidence of hypocalcemia after total thyroidectomy is lower when the surgery is performed by skilled surgeons.

References

1. Alqahtani SM: Awareness of thyroid disorders among the Saudi population. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2021; 15:1010-4.
2. Neri G, Castiello F, Vitullo F, De Rosa M, Ciammetti G, Croce A: Post-thyroidectomy dysphonia in patients with bilateral resection of the superior laryngeal nerve: a comparative spectrographic study. *Acta Otorhinolaryngol Ital.* 2011; 31:228-34.
3. Oertli D, Harder F. Surgical approach to thyroid nodules and cancer. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2000; 14:651-66.
4. Kwak HY, Dionigi G, Liu X, et al. Predictive factors for longer operative times for thyroidectomy. *Asian J Surg.* 2017; 40:139-44.
5. Karamanakis SN, Markou KB, Panagopoulos K, et al. Complications and risk factors related to the extent of surgery in thyroidectomy. Results from 2,043 procedures. *Hormones (Athens).* 2010; 9:318-25.
6. Alqahtani SM, Almussallam B, Alatawi AS, et al. Post-thyroidectomy complications and risk factors in Tabuk, Saudi Arabia: a retrospective cohort study. *Cureus.* 2020; 12:10.
7. Al-Qurayshi Z, Robins R, Hauch A, Randolph GW, Kandil E: Association of surgeon volume with outcomes and cost savings following thyroidectomy: a national forecast. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2016; 142:32-9.
8. Rosato L, Avenia N, Bernante P, et al.: Complications of thyroid surgery: analysis of a multicentric study on 14,934 patients operated on in Italy over 5 years. *World J Surg.* 2004; 28:271-6.
9. Khavanin N, Mlodinow A, Kim JY et al. Assessing Safety and Outcomes in Outpatient versus Inpatient Thyroidectomy using the NSQIP: A Propensity Score Matched Analysis

- of 16,370 Patients. *Ann Surg Oncol*.2014; 20 (3): 17-23.
10. Pullen L. Thyroid Surgery: Guidelines for Improving Voice Outcomes. *Medscape Medical News*. Thyroid Surgery: Guidelines for Improving Voice Outcomes. *Medscape Medical News*.2013 <https://www.medscape.com/viewarticle/805325>
 11. Chandrasekhar SS, Randolph GW, Seidman MD et al. Clinical practice guideline: improving voice outcomes after thyroid surgery. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*.2013; 148 (6):1-37.
 12. El Nemr S, Reda M, Hashish M, Amir H. Assessment of Hypocalcemia Following Total Thyroidectomy for Benign Thyroid Lesions: To Be Continued or Not?. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2019 Apr 1;75(1): 2105-11.
 13. Lee YS, Nam KH, Chung WY, Chang HS, Park CS: Postoperative complications of thyroid cancer in a single center experience. *J Korean Med Sci*. 2010; 25:541-5.
 14. Eismontas V, Slepavicius A, Janusonis V, et al. Predictors of postoperative hypocalcemia occurring after a total thyroidectomy: results of prospective multicenter study. *BMC Surg*. 2018; 18.
 15. Pflieger AG, Ahmad N, Draper MR, Vrotsou K, Smith WK: The timing of calcium measurements in helping to predict temporary and permanent hypocalcaemia in patients having completion and total thyroidectomies. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl*. 2009; 91:140-6.
 16. Trottier DC, Barron P, Moonje V, Tadros S. Outpatient thyroid surgery: Should patients be discharged on the day of their procedures? *Can J Surg*.2009; 52(3):182-6.
 17. Mehanna HM, Jain A, Randeve H et al. Postoperative Hypocalcemia: The difference a definition makes. *Head-Neck*.2010; 32(3):279-83.
 18. Asari R, Passler C, Kaczirek K et al. Hypoparathyroidism after total thyroidectomy: a prospective study. *Arch Surg*.2008; 143:132-7.
 19. Kerimoglu RS, Gozalan U, Kama NA. Complications of thyroid surgery: Analysis of 1159 cases. *IJMMS*.2013;1(3):35-38.
 20. Fahmy FF, Gillette D, Lolen Y et al. Management of serum calcium level in post thyroidectomy patients. *Clin Otolaryngol*.2004; 29(6): 735-39.
 21. Wiseman JE, Mossanen M, Ituarte PHG et al. An Algorithm Informed by the Parathyroid Hormone Level Reduces Hypocalcaemic Complications of Thyroidectomy. *World J Surg*.2010; 34:532-7.
 22. WU J, Harrison B. Hypocalcemia after Thyroidectomy: The Need for Improved Definitions. *WJOES*.2010; 2(1):17-20.
 23. Lo CY, Luk JM and Tam SC. Applicability of Intraoperative Parathyroid Hormone Assay During Thyroidectomy. *Ann Surg*.2002;236 (5):564-69.
 24. Tolone S, Roberto R, Del Genio G et al. The impact of age and oral calcium and vitamin D supplements on postoperative hypocalcemia after total thyroidectomy: A prospective study. *BMC Surgery*.2013; 13(2):S11.
 25. Kwon Y-H, Lee KE, Kwon H et al. Preoperative parathyroid hormone level as a predictive factor for post thyroidectomy hypoparathyroidism. *Korean J Clin Oncol*.2013; 9(1):28-32.
 26. Terris DJ, Snyder S, Carneiro-Pla D et al. The American Thyroid Association Surgical Affairs Committee Writing Task Force. American Thyroid Association Statement on Outpatient Thyroidectomy. *THYROID*.2013; 23(10): 1193-202.
 27. Lombardi CP, Raffaelli M, Princi P et al. Early prediction of post thyroidectomy hypocalcemia by one single iPTH measurement. *Surgery*. 2004; 136:1236-41
 28. Lam A, Kerr PD. Parathyroid hormone: an early predictor of post thyroidectomy hypocalcemia. *Laryngoscope*.2003; 113:2196-200.
 29. Pattou F, Combemale F, Fabre S et al. Hypocalcemia following thyroid surgery: incidence and prediction of outcome. *World J Surg*.1998; 22:718-24.
 30. Carter Y, Chen H and Sippel RS. An intact parathyroid hormone-based protocol for the prevention and treatment of symptomatic hypocalcemia after thyroidectomy. *J Surg Res*. 2014; 186(1):15-17.